

Thermophilic Biohydrogen and Organic Acid Production from Spoiled Fig Fruits through a Single-Stage Fermentation Process

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Abstract

One of the most effective ways to reduce the environmental impact caused by organic wastes and to achieve a circular economy and full decarbonization is to convert such wastes into industrial and value-added products such as organic acid, biofuels, etc. The aim of this study was to convert contaminated fig wastes with no commercial value into biohydrogen, organic acids and solvents such as ethanol-butanol-acetone by a one-stage consolidated fermentation method under thermophilic conditions (45 °C). Fig wastes were pre-treated by drying, shredding, grinding and sieving to obtain particle size $D_p=275 \mu\text{m}$. In order to release sugars that can be used by bacteria in fermentation, fig waste ground at 50 g/L was partially hydrolyzed for $t=60 \text{ min}$ and at $T=100 \text{ °C}$ and 45% sugar recovery was achieved. The effect of 10 g/L and 25 g/L initial fig waste concentration on the production of hydrogen and other by-products by dark consolidated fermentation was investigated. Total gas, biohydrogen gas percentage, sugar consumption, organic acid and solvent types and concentrations were monitored. The highest cumulative hydrogen volume (21.10 mL), hydrogen production yield (2.67 mol H_2/mol glucose) and hydrogen production rate (42.20 mL H_2/L) were obtained at 15 g/L fig waste concentration. In contrast, the highest fermentation by-products such as 2.78 g/L acetic acid, 0.19 g/L propionic acid, 2.56 g/L acetone, and 1.50 g/L ethanol are produced in the fermentation broth with a biowaste concentration of 20 g/L fig waste. The results show that the single-stage consolidated hydrogen fermentation approach is an effective method to convert contaminated fig fruits into valuable biofuels and organic acids, contributing to the circular economy and carbon neutrality target.

Keywords: Consolidated fermentation, biohydrogen, organic acids, solvent

Introduction

Organic waste constitutes a significant social issue affecting individuals and the environment. As per the definition given by The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), food waste is “food losses of quality and quantity through the process of the supply chain taking place at production, post-harvest, and processing stages” [1]. Specifically, food waste and fruit waste correspond to the loss of food at the end of food life cycle. Generation of these wastes also lead to considerable loss of other resources like water, land, labor and energy [2]. It was estimated by FAO that annually 1.3 billion tons food and fruits intended for human consumption are wasted globally. This wasted food is one-third of the total food produced globally, whose production corresponds from 28% of agricultural area utilizing 1.4 billion hectare of the world’s fertile land [3].

This staggering amount of fruit and food wastes have substantial social, economic, and environmental impacts, affecting farmers, food producers, and consumers alike. On a social level, the consequences are diverse, affecting individuals in various ways, including exacerbating hunger and malnutrition within communities [4]. Economically, inadequate storage, transportation, and distribution infrastructure lead to substantial losses for both farmers and industrialists when products are discarded, with the FAO estimating the annual direct economic loss at \$750 billion [5]. Environmentally, food waste contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane and carbon dioxide, upon decomposition [6]. Addressing this environmental impact is crucial for achieving a circular economy and complete decarbonization.

One effective approach involves reducing the environmental impact caused by organic waste through the conversion of waste into valuable products, a task for which fermentation technologies are often employed. Fermentation can occur as either dark fermentation, which takes place in the absence of light, or light fermentation, which occurs in an environment with sufficient light. Some of the products

of fermentation include gases (e.g., hydrogen, carbon dioxide, methane), organic acids (e.g., lactic acid, propionic acid, acetic acid and butyric acid), and solvents (e.g., acetone, ethanol, butanol) [7].

Biohydrogen is a form of hydrogen gas (H_2) produced through biological processes, typically by specific microorganisms under certain conditions. It is considered a renewable and clean energy source because its production generally involves biological reactions such as photosynthesis or the fermentation of organic matter. Various methods are available for biohydrogen production, including fermentation processes (dark fermentation and photofermentation), biophotolysis processes (direct and indirect biophotolysis), and electrohydrogenesis processes [8]. Dark fermentative biohydrogen production is a renewable form of hydrogen generation in the presence of anaerobic microorganisms capable of utilizing carbon-rich substrates for biohydrogen production. Photofermentative hydrogen production refers to H_2 formation from the degradation of organic carbon sources by purple non-sulfur bacteria under anaerobic conditions and light [9]. Dark fermentation is preferred over light fermentation due to its simplicity, production efficiency, and speed. The theoretical production efficiency in dark fermentation is 4 mol H_2 /mol glucose in the case of glucose conversion to acetic acid and 2 mol H_2 /mol glucose in the formation of butyric acid. The accepted efficiency coefficient in the literature is 2.5-3.0 mol H_2 /mol glucose [10–12]. The production rate varies depending on the substrate type and fermentation technology. The percentage of H_2 in the total gas produced can reach up to 80% [13].

Hydrogen production through biological processes offers several advantages. These technologies are less energy-intensive, environmentally friendly, and utilize renewable resources such as agricultural waste, wastewater, and organic residues [8]. Thus, they reduce waste amounts and enhance sustainability [14]. Additionally, the biological production process emits minimal greenhouse gases compared to traditional hydrogen production methods that rely on fossil fuels [15].

Dark fermentation is utilized for the production of biohydrogen from agricultural waste, lignocellulosic residues, municipal solid waste, kitchen waste, and vegetable and fruit waste [16,17]. Among these substrates, fruit waste stands out as an ideal substrate for biohydrogen production due to its characteristics such as high moisture content, high volatile solid content, biodegradability with nutrient and high sugar concentrations [18,19].

Fig is a high-value economic product and becomes contaminated with toxic substances such as aflatoxin within 7 days if not properly preserved [20]. Contaminated figs are disposed of in incinerators, consuming high energy during disposal, and uncontrolled CO_2 emissions occur due to the carbon content of the biomass. Therefore, it is imperative to valorize contaminated fig waste through sustainable approaches, converting it into bioenergy and bioproducts. Abibu et al. [21] investigated the total sugar content from 100 g/L contaminated figs and obtained 82 g/L total sugar using acidic conditions with microwave-assisted pre-treatment and 70 g/L total sugar using acidic conditions with steam-assisted autoclave pre-treatment.

Due to the cost and the formation of toxic substances of pre-treatments, the transition to consolidated fermentation process as a single-step biological hydrolysis and fermentation process has begun [22]. For this purpose, natural bacteria that provide cellulose solubilization or genetically modified bacteria can be used. In consolidated fermentation for hydrogen production from cellulose and hemicellulose-containing wastes, thermophilic bacteria of *Caldicellulosiruptor* sp., *Clostridium thermocellum*, and *Thermoanaerobacterium* sp. and mesophilic bacteria of *Thermotoga* sp. and *Clostridium* sp. are used [23,24]. Due to the limited number of bacteria capable of hydrolyzing cellulose, consolidated fermentation of lignocellulosic waste is relatively more difficult. However, fruit waste has a high simple sugar content, and therefore, various bacteria can hydrolyze it. The aim of this study was to produce biohydrogen, organic acids, acetone, and ethanol from contaminated fig fruit waste using the consolidated fermentation method under thermophilic conditions (45°C).

Material and Methods

Equipment, Chemicals, and Standards

The equipment used in the study includes an oven (JEIOTECH GC 300/1000), autoclave (Hirayama HVE-50), electric grinder (Demsan Terazi, Istanbul/Türkiye), sieve (Retsch AS 200 BASIC), HPLC (Agilent), UV-visible spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 Bio model), and GC TCD. The chemicals used in microorganism growth, fermentation, and analyses are of high purity and include CH_3COOH (Fluka Chemie GmbH), $C_3H_6O_2$ (Fluka Chemie GmbH), C_2H_6O (Fluka Chemie GmbH), C_3H_6O (Fluka Chemie GmbH), $C_6H_{12}O_6$, NaOH, H_2SO_4 , $CaCO_3$, phenol, yeast extract, and L-cysteine.

Substrate and Partial Hydrolysis

The waste figs used in this study were obtained from the Aegean Exporters Association in İzmir, Turkey. The figs were initially reduced to a size of approximately ≤ 3 cm and then dried in an oven at 75 °C for 72 hours. The dried figs were ground in a mechanical grinder to reduce particle size. The ground figs were sieved in the Mining Engineering Department Laboratories to classify particle size. A particle size of $D_p \approx 275$ μm was used in the experimental studies.

The ground fig wastes were subjected to partial hydrolysis by boiling at 100 °C, allowing easily soluble simple sugars to transfer into the liquid phase (Figure 1). Fifteen minutes after the start of hydrolysis, the first 5 mL hydrolysate aliquot was collected, the next three aliquots were collected at 30-minute intervals, and the remaining aliquots were collected at 1-hour intervals until the concentration reached a constant value. The sugar recovery rate was determined (% sugar/fig waste, w/w). The purpose of partial hydrolysis is to provide the minimum carbon source needed for microorganisms to grow at the start of fermentation. The aim is not to recover all the sugar concentration in the fig. Therefore, the partial hydrolysis time that achieves a 10%-20% sugar recovery is considered sufficient for the subsequent consolidated fermentation.

Figure 1. Pre-treatment of fig wastes

Microorganism

The bacterium culture *C. pasteurianum* DSM 525 was obtained from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH. Prior to fermentation, the bacterial culture was enriched by growing it in a medium containing 40 g/L glucose, 20 g/L CaCO_3 , 10 g/L yeast extract, and 0.1 g/L L-cysteine at 37 °C and pH 7.0 for 24 hours under anaerobic conditions.

Fermentation

Fermentation studies were conducted in 310 mL serum bottles with a reaction volume of 200 mL under anaerobic conditions at 45 °C in batch and static conditions. The fermentation medium was composed of partially hydrolyzed fig at an initial biomass concentration of 10-25 g/L, 20 g/L CaCO_3 , 10 g/L yeast extract, and 0.1 g/L L-cysteine. To ensure anaerobic conditions, L-cysteine was added as an oxygen-scavenging chemical to the medium, and nitrogen gas was passed through the gas phase to sweep out oxygen. During fermentation, the pH was checked daily and adjusted to pH 6.5-7.0 by adding dilute NaOH. No external nitrogen, phosphorus, or other nutrients were added to the medium. The stock culture volume added to the fermentation medium was 50 mL, constituting 25% of the fermentation reaction liquid volume.

Analytical Methods

Sampling

Samples taken daily were centrifuged at 7800 rpm for 20 min (Figure 2). The microorganisms were separated, and the liquid phase obtained was stored at +4 °C for analyses.

Total Sugar Analysis

The phenol-sulfuric acid method, a spectrophotometric method, was used for total sugar analysis. A 5% phenol solution and concentrated sulfuric acid were used [25]. Samples were prepared in glass tubes by adding 1 mL sample (at appropriate dilution), 1 mL phenol solution, and 5 mL H₂SO₄ and allowed to cool at room temperature for approximately 20 min. The absorbance values of the samples were read at 490 nm wavelength using a quartz cuvette in an UV-vis spectrophotometer. Glucose standard samples were prepared using the same method. The absorbance/concentration calibration curve was used for concentration calculation.

Hydrogen Measurements

The total gas volume produced was determined using a gas-liquid displacement system based on the principle of communicating vessels (Figure 2). The liquid solution consisted of a mixture of 2% H₂SO₄ and 10% NaCl. Hydrogen gas measurements were performed using an Agilent 6890 (Varian 3600) Gas Chromatography. The column used was Alltech, Hayesep D 80/100 6" x 1/8" x 0.085"; the detector was a thermal conductivity detector (TCD); and the carrier gas was N₂ (30 mL/min). The oven temperature was 35 °C, injection temperature 200 °C, and filament 140 °C. The hydrogen concentration of the total gas taken from the fermentation medium was measured using a gas-tight glass syringe. Cumulative hydrogen volume and hydrogen production rate were also determined.

Organic Acid and Solvent Analysis

Acetic acid, propionic acid, ethanol, and acetone concentrations were determined using HPLC (Figure 2). The mobile phase was 5 mM H₂SO₄ with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. The column was Aminex HPX-87H Ion Exclusion Column 300 mm x 7.8 mm. Organic acid analyses were conducted with diode array detector at 40 °C oven temperature and 210 nm wavelength. Solvent analyses were conducted with refractive index detector at 40 °C temperature.

Figure 2. Fermentation, hydrogen measurements, organic acid, and solvent analyses

Results and Discussion

Partial Hydrolysis of Fig Waste with Heat Treatment

Fig waste at a biomass concentration of 50 g/L was partially hydrolyzed by heating at 100°C for up to 4 hours, monitored periodically for sugar measurements. The purpose of hydrolysis was to extract soluble sugars at sufficient levels to support microbial growth and maintain their viability during fermentation. A 5 mL aliquot of hydrolysate was first collected 15 min after the start of hydrolysis, followed by three aliquots at 30-minute intervals, and the remaining portions were collected at 1-hour intervals. The total sugar concentration increased to 21 g/L within the first 15 min, achieving a sugar recovery of 42.28% (21.14 g Total sugar/50 g fig waste). Approximately 135 min later, an increasing trend in sugar concentration reaching 26 g/L was observed, and the recovery rate increased to 52% (Figure 3). A 10% improvement in sugar recovery was recorded after approximately 2.5-hour of heat treatment. During continued heat treatment, the total sugar concentration reached 30 g/L, achieving a recovery rate of 58-61% by 255 min (4.25-hour).

Sugar is a critical raw material in the production of high value-added products from organic waste through fermentation. Although maximum sugar recovery is the goal of hydrolysis, its economic

feasibility is also crucial. Approximately a 20% increase in sugar concentration was achieved relative to the energy consumed after applying heat treatment for about 4.2 hours. Considering system economy and practicality, 1 hour of heat treatment was deemed sufficient in the current study. Therefore, in subsequent studies, 1 hour of heat treatment was applied to the fig waste during substrate preparation. Additionally, in consolidated fermentation, bacterial hydrolysis must continue during fermentation, rendering prolonged and costly hydrolysis processes unnecessary.

Figure 3. Variation of total sugar concentration and sugar recovery percentage in time obtained from heat-hydrolyzed fig wastes

Hydrogen Gas Production via Consolidated Fermentation under Thermophilic (45°C) Conditions

Consolidated batch dark fermentations were conducted under thermophilic conditions using *C. pasteurianum* with contaminated fig fruit (10-25 g/L) as previously described in an experimental section. Dark fermentation is a process that produces hydrogen gas from various organic substrates including agricultural residues, food wastes, and other energy-rich biomasses in the absence of light [26].

In the fermentation study using fig waste at a biomass concentration of 10 g/L, hydrogen production reached 8.75 mL after 24 hours of fermentation (Figure 4). Hydrogen production remained constant throughout the 96-hour fermentation period following this increase. The production efficiency based on added hydrogen volume was 0.16 mol H₂/mol glucose, and the volumetric hydrogen production rate was 43.73 mL/L·day. The initial total sugar content was the amount of sugar released after partial hydrolysis, which was 6 g/L in this experimental study. During the fermentation process, sugar concentration decreased by only 2 g/L, dropping to 4 g/L. The limited sugar consumption indicates slow metabolism of microorganisms. Moreover, in consolidated fermentation, sugar consumption and bacterial hydrolysis of organic particles are expected to occur, leading to sugar release. The absence of sugar consumption in consolidated fermentation at 10 g/L fig waste or 6 g/L sugar concentration indicates that bacterial hydrolysis did not occur. Limited hydrogen production occurred as a result of the lack of sugar consumption.

Figure 4. Variation of hydrogen production and total sugar formation from fig waste at 10 g/L concentration

In the fermentation study with fig waste at a biomass concentration of 15 g/L, hydrogen production was 16.45 mL after 24 hours of fermentation. No change in hydrogen volume was observed up to 48-hour, with production occurring in the subsequent period and an increase in hydrogen volume observed at low rates (Figure 5). Cumulative hydrogen yield (2.67 mol H₂/mol glucose) and volumetric hydrogen production rate of 82.25 mL/L·day were achieved at this biomass concentration. Looking at the sugar consumption profile, initial sugar concentration was 11 g/L, which decreased slowly and reached 5 g/L by the 72-hour. Sugar consumption occurred, with approximately 50% of the sugar being consumed indicating that microbial metabolism slowed down. However, after the 72-hour in consolidated fermentation, bacterial hydrolysis occurred, increasing sugar concentration to around 10 g/L. In other words, bacterial hydrolysis occurred, and fermentation proceeded according to the consolidated fermentation principle. Dark fermentation biohydrogen production can occur via acetate production or butyrate production routes. In dark fermentation of acetic acid (Eq. 1), glucose metabolism results in the production of 2 mol hydrogen molecules and 4 mol acetate [27]. In contrast, butyric acid dark fermentation (Eq. 2) yields 1 mol butyrate and 2 mol hydrogen molecules through the metabolic process. The obtained efficiency coefficient of 2.67 mol H₂/mol glucose could approach the theoretical value achievable via acetic-butyric acid fermentation route, with the increase in sugar contributing to this high efficiency coefficient.

Acetate-type dark fermentation

Butyrate-type dark fermentation

Results of the fermentation study at a biomass concentration of 20 g/L are shown in Figure 6. Hydrogen gas production reached a maximum volume of 15.05 mL after the first 24 hours. The hydrogen efficiency obtained after the initial 24 hours was 1.95 mol H₂/mol glucose, approaching the theoretical efficiency. There was a partial increase in hydrogen volume from 24 to 96 hours of fermentation, with the added volume reaching up to 20 mL. The production efficiency at the end of fermentation was 1.19 mol H₂/mol glucose. Examining total sugar consumption, it remained unchanged at 10 g/L sugar concentration in the initial 24 hours and then decreased to 5 g/L by the 72-hour. Microbial hydrolysis in consolidated fermentation began after 72 hours, increasing sugar concentration to around 9 g/L. The highest volumetric production rate achieved at this fig waste concentration was 75.25 mL/L·day.

Figure 5. Changes in hydrogen production and total sugar production over time from fig waste at 15 g/L concentration

Figure 6. Changes in hydrogen production and total sugar production over time from fig waste at 20 g/L concentration

Figure 7. Changes over time in hydrogen production and total sugar production from fig waste at 25 g/L biomass concentration

In the fermentation study using fig waste at a biomass concentration of 25 g/L, hydrogen production was 15.53 mL 24 hours after the start of fermentation (Figure 7). Subsequently, there was no significant increase in hydrogen volume between 48 and 98 hours. The cumulative hydrogen yield obtained (0.64

mol H₂/mol glucose) was lower than observed at fig concentrations of 15 and 20 g/L. The maximum hydrogen production rate at this biomass concentration was 77.63 mL/L·day. According to the consolidated fermentation principle, sugar consumption profile decreased at the beginning of fermentation and then increased with microbial hydrolysis. Biohydrogen, a renewable and clean energy source produced through biological reactions, is essential in the current energy transition due to its efficiency and environmentally friendly nature [8]. It does not produce polluting by-products during combustion, facilitates long-distance storage and transport via hydrogen liquefaction, and significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions [8,28].

Production of Organic Acids and Solvents via Consolidated Fermentation under Thermophilic (45°C) Conditions

Besides hydrogen gas, dark fermentation also produces valuable byproducts such as carbon dioxide, solvents (e.g., acetone, butanol, ethanol), and organic acids (e.g., acetic acid, butyric acid, lactic acid, propionic acid). Considering this, the present study analyzed the solvents (acetone and ethanol) and organic acids (acetic and propionic acid) in the fermentation products (Table 1). Lactic acid was not detected in any of the fermentation setups.

Table 1. Organic acids and solvents from fig waste at different concentrations

Time (h)	Acetic acid g/L	Propionic acid g/L	Ethanol g/L	Acetone g/L
10g Fig /L				
0	0.84	0.07	nd	nd
24	1.03	nd	1.11	1.96
48	1.03	0.08	0.50	2.06
72	1.67	0.14	1.01	2.21
96	1.78	0.15	0.77	2.34
15 g Fig /L				
0	0.75	nd	nd	nd
24	1.43	0.10	0.35	2.04
48	0.06	nd	1.01	0.72
72	1.56	0.15	1.13	2.21
96	nd	nd	0.02	0.52
20 g Fig /L				
0	nd	nd	nd	nd
24	0.98	nd	nd	1.96
48	1.50	nd	1.35	2.19
72	1.83	0.15	1.33	2.30
96	2.39	0.16	1.50	2.42
144	2.78	0.19	1.14	2.56
25g Fig /L				
0	0.71	nd	nd	nd
24	1.02	0.10	1.48	2.02
48	nd	nd	0.91	0.67
72	1.71	0.17	1.69	2.41
96	2.32	0.19	1.55	2.50

nd – not detected

In the fermentation investigation involving fig waste at a biomass concentration of 10 g/L, the analysis revealed the presence of acetic acid (0.84 - 1.78 g/L), propionic acid (0.07 - 0.15 g/L), ethanol

(0.50 - 1.11 g/L), and acetone (1.96 - 2.34 g/L). Notably, the concentrations of these identified organic acids and acetone increased with the progression of fermentation time. This pattern was also observed in fermentations with fig waste concentrations of 20 g/L and 25 g/L. At 20 g/L, acetic acid (0.98 - 2.78 g/L), propionic acid (0.15 - 0.19 g/L), ethanol (1.14 - 1.50 g/L), and acetone (1.96 - 2.56 g/L) were detected. At 25 g/L, the analysis showed acetic acid (0.71 - 2.32 g/L), propionic acid (0.10 - 0.19 g/L), ethanol (0.91 - 1.69 g/L), and acetone (0.67 - 2.50 g/L). It should be noted that the fermentation time for the 20 g/L fig waste substrate was extended up to 144 hours. In contrast, the results obtained at a fig waste concentration of 15 g/L showed significantly lower concentrations of acetic acid (0.06 - 1.56 g/L), propionic acid (0.10 - 0.15 g/L), ethanol (0.02 - 1.13 g/L), and acetone (0.52 - 2.21 g/L), which did not increase with extended fermentation time. The absence of lactic acid in this study may be associated with the higher yield of hydrogen observed. Theoretically, hydrogen is not produced during the formation of lactic acid. Consequently, it can be deduced that the carbon sources in the fermentation medium were directed towards hydrogen generation and acetic acid synthesis. Additionally, acetic acid can be converted to acetone, which may explain the relatively high amount of acetone obtained in this study.

Conclusion

In the present study, the release of soluble sugars suitable for fermentation was achieved through partial hydrolysis with short-term heat treatment. It was also observed that bacterial hydrolysis occurs during fermentation, transferring residual sugars to the liquid phase and resulting in a relative increase in sugar concentration in some instances. The cumulative hydrogen yield and production rate were notably higher, particularly in fermentation setups with fig waste concentrations of 15 g/L and 20 g/L. As expected, organic acids and solvents were also found in relatively high concentrations, with the highest concentrations observed at a substrate concentration of 20 g/L. The absence of lactic acid likely contributed to the high hydrogen productivity observed in this study. In conclusion, the results suggest that the single-stage hydrogen fermentation approach is an efficient method for converting spoiled fig fruits into valuable biofuels and organic acids, thereby contributing to the circular economy and decarbonization efforts.

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